

All interactions				Generalist-Generalist				Generalist-Specialist				Specialist-Specialist			
Estimate	Cond..SE	t.value		Estimate	Cond..SE	t.value		Estimate	Cond..SE	t.value		Estimate	Cond..SE	t.value	
fixed effects (beta)				fixed effects (beta)				fixed effects (beta)				fixed effects (beta)			
(Intercept)	0.017	0.028	0.606	(Intercept)	0.03	0.026	1.156	(Intercept)	0.077	0.049	1.552	(Intercept)	0.017	0.023	0.742
num. of species	-0.013	0.001	-10.428	num. of generalists	0.013	0.002	6.189	num. of species	-0.014	0.002	-8.093	num. of specialists	-0.009	0.001	-7.175
ecological overlap	0.668	0.011	59.096	ecological overlap	0.415	0.008	52.324	ecological overlap	0.421	0.015	27.939	ecological overlap	0.701	0.015	46.463
num. of species x ecological overlap	-0.015	0.002	-7.934	num. of species x ecological overlap	0	0.002	0.049	num. of species x ecological overlap	0.002	0.003	0.722	num. of species x ecological overlap	0.005	0.005	1.057
Random effects				Random effects				Random effects				Random effects			
nu	0.602			nu	0.697			nu	0.633			nu	0.455		
rho	0.077			rho	0.09			rho	0.036			rho	0.048		
lambda (x+y)	0.009			lambda (x+y)	0.007			lambda (x+y)	0.012			lambda (x+y)	0.003		
Residual variance				Residual variance				Residual variance				Residual variance			
phi	1e-06			phi	1e-06			phi	1e-06			phi	1e-06		
Likelihood values				Likelihood values				Likelihood values				Likelihood values			
logLik	5286.622			logLik	4525.269			logLik	2044.219			logLik	4474.289		